

Supplementary information

A multicolor bioluminescent toolbox for multiplex glow-in-the-dark nucleic acid diagnostics

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gRNA, primer, target DNA and protein sequences

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Matlab script for processing camera pictures

```
% extraction all photo names from folder
jpgFiles = dir('*.JPG');
numFiles = length(jpgFiles);
% reading in all RGB images
for k = 1:numFiles
    mydata{k} = imread(jpgFiles(k).name);
end
% use image to extract circle coordinates
for k = 1
    subplot(2, 1, 1)
    imshow(mydata{k});% Get the gray image
    grayImage = im2gray(mydata{k});
    % enhance contrast
    contrastImage = adapthisteq(grayImage);
    % Remove noise
    filteredImage = medfilt2(contrastImage);
    n = 8; %filter steps
    for i = 1:n
        filteredImage = medfilt2(filteredImage);
    end
    % Get the binary image
    binaryImage = im2bw(filteredImage, 0.1);
    % display binary image
    subplot(2, 1, 2);
    imshow(binaryImage);
    % find and visualize circles
    stats = regionprops('table', binaryImage, 'Centroid', 'Eccentricity', 'EquivDiameter');
    stats(stats.EquivDiameter < 120, :) = [];
    statsArray = table2array(stats);
    centers = statsArray(:,1:2);
    diameter = statsArray(:,4);
    radii = diameter/3;
    viscircles(centers, radii,'EdgeColor','r');
end
% extracting g/b ratios from all images and all wells
BRcombined = [];
GRcombined = [];
Bcombined = [];
Gcombined = [];
```

```

for k = 1:numFiles
    R = mydata{k}(:,:,1);
    G = mydata{k}(:,:,2);
    B = mydata{k}(:,:,3);
    for n = 1: length(radii)
        mask = circles2mask(centers(n,1:2), radii(n,1), size(binaryImage));
        mean_R = mean(R(mask));
        mean_G = mean(G(mask)) - 0.1*mean(B(mask));
        mean_B = mean(B(mask)) - 0.2*mean(G(mask));
        BRvalue = mean_B/mean_R;
        GRvalue = mean_G/mean_R;
        Bcombined = [Bcombined, mean_B];
        Gcombined = [Gcombined, mean_G];
        BRcombined = [BRcombined, BRvalue];
        GRcombined = [GRcombined, GRvalue];
    end
end
% Combine all G/B values in array
BRfinal = reshape(BRcombined, length(radii), []);
GRfinal = reshape(GRcombined, length(radii), []);
Bfinal = reshape(Bcombined, length(radii), []);
Gfinal = reshape(Gcombined, length(radii), []);
% Compute moving mean over values
BRsmooth = [];
GRsmooth = [];
Bsmooth = [];
Gsmooth = [];
numWells = length(radii);
numMean = 5; %computes mean over every 5 values
for n = 1 : numWells
    BRvector = BRfinal(n, :);
    GRvector = GRfinal(n, :);
    Bvector = Bfinal(n, :);
    Gvector = Gfinal(n, :);
    BRaverage = movmean(BRvector, numMean);
    GRaverage = movmean(GRvector, numMean);
    Baverage = movmean(Bvector, numMean);
    Gaverage = movmean(Gvector, numMean);
    BRsmooth = [BRsmooth, BRaverage];
    GRsmooth = [GRsmooth, GRaverage];
    Bsmooth = [Bsmooth, Baverage];

```

```

    Gsmooth = [Gsmooth, Gaverage];
end

%Combine all averaged values in array
BRsmooth_final = reshape(BRsmooth, [numFiles, numWells]);
GRsmooth_final = reshape(GRsmooth, [numFiles, numWells]);
Bsmooth_final = reshape(Bsmooth, [numFiles, numWells]);
Gsmooth_final = reshape(Gsmooth, [numFiles, numWells]);

% add X,Y coordinates of wells
BRsmooth_final(numFiles+1, :) = centers(:,1);
BRsmooth_final(numFiles+2, :) = centers(:,2);
GRsmooth_final(numFiles+1, :) = centers(:,1);
GRsmooth_final(numFiles+2, :) = centers(:,2);
Bsmooth_final(numFiles+1, :) = centers(:,1);
Bsmooth_final(numFiles+2, :) = centers(:,2);
Gsmooth_final(numFiles+1, :) = centers(:,1);
Gsmooth_final(numFiles+2, :) = centers(:,2);

```

Supplementary Figures

Figure S1 | Expression and purification of LUNAS mNeonGreen fusion proteins. Reducing SDS-PAGE analysis of Strep-Tactin XT chromatography purification fractions of SpdCas9-SBiT-mNG (MW = 188.1), SpdCas9-LBiT-mNG (MW = 204.2 kDa), SpdCas9-mNG-SBiT (MW = 188.5 kDa) and SpdCas9-mNG-LBiT (MW = 203.9 kDa). L = Ladder (Precision Plus Protein™ marker (BioRad)), Lys = lysate, P = lysate pellet, SN = lysate supernatant, FT = flowthrough, W = wash, E = eluate.

Figure S2 | Green luminescence intensities of green LUNAS variants. Comparison of green luminescence (533 nm) intensities for different combinations of LUNAS-mNeonGreen fusion proteins and original LUNAS proteins. LUNAS reactions were performed using 500 pM target DNA (synthetic SARS-CoV-2 ORF1a fragment), 10 nM dCas9-SBiT:gRNA_SC2ORF1a_A variant and 1 nM dCas9-LBiT:gRNA_SC2ORF1a_B variant, and 2000x diluted NanoGlo in LUNAS RNP buffer. Bars represent average values and circles represent individual measurement (n = 3).

Figure S3 | Version of main figure 2D not corrected for spectral bleed-through. One-pot RPA-LUNAS for SARS-CoV-2 DNA performed with either blue LUNAS or green LUNAS. The left panel shows blue luminescence (458 nm) intensity, the right panel shows green luminescence (533 nm) intensity of both experiments. Assays were performed with 1000 cp of synthetic target DNA input, using 10 nM dCas9-SB:gRNA_ORF1a_A, 1 nM dCas9-LB:gRNA_ORF1a_B in a 20 μ L reaction. Individual replicate traces (n = 2) are shown, with a rolling average filter (7-point centered) applied to the luminescence readings, without spectral unmixing correction applied.

Figure S4 | Expression and purification of NanoLuc cysteine mutants for maleimide dye coupling. Reducing SDS-PAGE analysis of Ni-NTA IMAC purification fractions of NL*_T41C, NL*_G66C, NL*_S68C, NL*_G136C, NL*_G159C, and NL*_G113C, with NL* indicating the NanoLuc mutant with native cysteine mutated to serine (C166S). MW of all variants is 22,1 kDa. L = Ladder (Precision Plus Protein™ marker (BioRad)), P = lysate pellet, SN = lysate supernatant, FT = flowthrough, W = wash, E = eluate.

Figure S5 | Luminescence intensities of unconjugated and ATTO490LS-conjugated NanoLuc mutants for red calibrator variants. (A) Comparison of blue luminescence (458 nm) intensities of the various NanoLuc Cysteine mutants (having C166S + indicated Cys introducing mutation) and original NanoLuc (wt, S166). (B) Comparison of red luminescence (653 nm) intensities of the various NanoLuc-ATTO490LS conjugates and original NanoLuc (wt). Measurements for both (A) and (B) were carried out using 1 nM luciferase (conjugate) in PBS with 0.1% (w/v) BSA and 1000x diluted NanoGlo. Bars represent average values and circles represent individual replicate values (n = 3).

Figure S6 | ESI-QTOF mass spectra of NanoLuc-ATTO490LS conjugate variants, before and after dye coupling. Theoretical masses: NL*_{T41C} = 22.085 kDa; NL*_{T41C}-ATTO490LS = 22.881 kDa; NL*_{G66C} = 22.129 kDa; NL*_{G66C}-ATTO490LS = 22.925 kDa; NL*_{S68C} = 22.099 kDa; NL*_{S68C}-ATTO490LS = 22.895 kDa; NL*_{G113C} = 22.129 kDa; NL*_{G113C}-ATTO490LS = 22.925 kDa; NL*_{G136C} = 22.129 kDa; NL*_{G136C}-ATTO490LS = 22.925 kDa; NL*_{G159C} = 22.129 kDa; NL*_{G159C}-ATTO490LS = 22.925 kDa. NL* indicates NanoLuc with C166S mutation.

Figure S7 | Calibrator luciferases comparison. Top: comparison of absolute luminescence intensities between the split NanoLuc (blue split calibrator), split NanoLuc-mNeongreen (green split calibrator) and split NanoLuc-ATTO490LS (red split calibrator). Measurements were carried out using 100 pM calibrator luciferase in PBS with 0.1% (w/v) BSA and 1000x diluted NanoGlo. Lines connect mean values (n = 3 individual sensor dilution preparations) and circles represent individual replicate values.

Figure S8 | Expression of split NanoLuc (NanoBiT, fragments fused together) with T41C mutation and ATTO490LS maleimide dye coupling. Reducing SDS-PAGE analysis of Ni-NTA IMAC purified NB_T41C (MW = 23.0 kDa) and the PD-10 purified NB_T41C-ATTO490LS conjugate. Left image shows Coomassie stain, and the right image shows a fluorescence photo (Cytiva Amersham IQ800, excitation λ = 460 nm, Cy5 emission filter) of the same gel pre-coomassie staining.

Figure S9 | ESI-QTOF mass spectra of the split NanoLuc red calibrator luciferase (NB_T41C-ATTO490LS), before and after dye coupling. Theoretical masses (first methionine truncated): NB_T41C = 22.859 kDa; NB_T41C-ATTO490LS = 23.655 kDa. The secondary peaks shifted +178 Da can likely be attributed to an α -N-gluconoyl modification on either of the two hexa-histidine tags present in the protein¹.

Figure S10 | Expression and purification of LUNAS proteins with cysteine mutations for maleimide dye labeling. Reducing SDS-PAGE analysis of Strep-Tactin XT chromatography purification fractions of SpdCas9*-SBI_T_K-4C (MW = 162.8 kDa), SpdCas9*-SBI_T_S+2C (MW = 162.8 kDa), SpdCas9*-LBI_T_T41C (MW = 178.9 kDa) and SpdCas9*-LBI_T_G66C (MW = 178.9 kDa), with SpdCas9* indicating the Cysteine-free SpdCas9 mutant (C80S, C574S). L = Ladder (Precision Plus Protein™ marker (BioRad)), SN = lysate supernatant, FT = flowthrough, W = wash, E = eluate.

Figure S11 | Red luminescence intensities of red LUNAS variants. Comparison of red luminescence (653 nm) intensities for different combinations of ATTO490LS-coupled LUNAS proteins and original LUNAS proteins (data for original LUNAS was obtained in a separate measurement). LUNAS reactions were performed using 500 pM target DNA (synthetic T7 fragment with 50 bp interspace), 10 nM dCas9*-SBiT:gRNA_T7A variant and 1 nM dCas9*-LBiT:gRNA_T7B variant, and 2000x diluted NanoGlo in LUNAS RNP buffer. Bars represent average values and circles represent individual measurement (n = 3).

Figure S12 | Comparison of LUNAS color variants sensor response. Comparison of sensor response over a range of target DNA concentrations between the blue, and the optimal green (i.e. dCas9-mNG-LBiT + dCas9-SBiT-mNG) and red LUNAS (i.e. dCas9*-LBiT_T41C-ATTO490LS + dCas9*-SBiT_K-4C-ATTO490LS) variants. Measurements were carried out using 10 nM LUNAS-SBiT and 1 nM LUNAS-LBiT variant RNPs in LUNAS RNP buffer with 2100x diluted NanoGlo. The SARS-CoV-2 ORF1a LUNAS gRNAs and target DNA fragment were used. Lines connect mean values (n = 3), and circles represent individual replicate values. *Intensity values are dependent on conditions incl. the specific assay and plate reader used, as well as measurement timing and temperature. Different LUNAS assays show different maximal signal and signal/background ratios.

Figure S13 | Optimizing primer ratio for one-pot RPA-LUNAS assay detecting HsRPP30 and SARS-CoV-2 ORF1a cDNA. Blue LUNAS is used to detect SARS-CoV-2 ORF1a target DNA, while green LUNAS detects human RPP30 target DNA. No calibrator luciferase was included in this screening experiment. SARS-CoV-2 ORF1a and HsRPP30 RPA primer molar ratios were varied from 1:1 to 3:1, keeping the ORF1a primers concentration constant at 480 nM each. The NTC and single primer set controls were only performed using the same primer concentrations as the final 3:1 ratio assay. Assays were performed with 2000 cp of synthetic target DNA input, using 1 nM dCas9-LB:gRNA_SC2ORF1a_B; 10 nM dCas9-SB:gRNA_SC2ORF1a_A; 2 nM dCas9-mNG-LB:gRNA_HsRPP30_B; 20 nM dCas9-SB-mNG:gRNA_HsRPP30_A in a 20 μ L reaction. Individual replicate traces ($n = 2$) of luminescence intensities in blue (458 nm) and green (533 nm) color channels are shown, corrected for spectral bleed-through, assuming for spillover (relative to peak signal) for green LUNAS: blue = 7%; for blue LUNAS: green = 15%, and with a rolling average filter (7-point centered) applied. Delayed signal onset and increased initial background signal compared to other results in this work is likely due to the use of a 384-wells plate in the platereader for this experiment, with reactions heating more slowly via convective heat transfer only.

A

B

Figure S14 | Duplex one-pot RPA-LUNAS assay using green and red LUNAS. Red LUNAS is used to detect SARS-CoV-2 ORF1a target DNA, while green LUNAS detects human RPP30 target DNA. (A) Green/Blue (533/458 nm) and Red/Blue (653/458 nm) ratio traces ($n = 2$), with a bleed-through correction (green = green $- 0.03 * \text{red}$, red = red $- 0.01 * \text{green}$) and with a rolling average filter (7-point centered) applied. Assays were performed with 1000 cp of synthetic target DNA input, 160 nM of both RPP30 primers and 480 nM SARS-CoV-2 primers, using 2 nM dCas9-LB_T41C-ATTO490LS:gRNA_SC2ORF1a_B; 20 nM dCas9-SB_K-4C-ATTO490LS:gRNA_SC2ORF1a_A; 2 nM dCas9-mNG-LB:gRNA_HsRPP30_B; 20 nM dCas9-SB-mNG:gRNA_HsRPP30_A and 2 pM of wildtype NanoLuc in a 20 μL reaction. (B) Luminescence intensities in blue (458 nm), green (533 nm) and red (653 nm) color channels, without spectral bleed-through correction. Individual replicate traces ($n = 2$) are shown.

Figure S15 | gRNA and primer screening for dcmH target (NG) using one-pot RPA-LUNAS with the blue LUNAS. Different graphs represent a different gRNA set and different colors represent different primer combination. Lines represent single measurements (n = 1).

Figure S16 | gRNA and primer screening for uvrC target (CT) using one-pot RPA-LUNAS with the blue LUNAS. Different graphs represent a different gRNA set and different colors represent different primer combination. Lines represent single measurements (n = 1).

Figure S17 | Additional reverse primer screening for *uvrC* target (CT) using a previously established gRNA combination (CT011 and CT012) in a one-pot RPA-LUNAS with the blue LUNAS. Different graphs represent a different forward RPA primers set while different colors represent different reverse RPA primers. Lines represent single measurements ($n = 1$).

Figure S18 | Additional primer screening for CT/NG duplex RPA-LUNAS in presence of full genomic DNA. As target input, a DNA isolate from a CT+ ($C_t = 29.0$) and NG+ ($C_t = 20$) double-positive clinical sample was used. As primer sets may interfere with each other, different combinations were tested, screening for fast signal offset and high maximal signal for both targets. The dark blue lines indicates the combination of optimal primers set from the single LUNAS assays, whereas light blue and green lines indicate exchange of *dcmH*, *uvrC* or both primer sets with other RPA primer sets targeting the same genes. Grey line represent no-template control (water, NTC). Graph shows response of the green LUNAS targeting *dcmH* (NG). LUNAS response to *uvrC* (CT) remained similar between combinations (data not shown). Lines represent single measurements ($n = 1$).

Figure S19 | Blue-, green- en red-light intensities of final one-pot duplex NG/CT RPA-LUNAS assay for dcmH target (NG, left) and uvrC target (CT, right). Assays were performed with 10 – 10,000 cp of synthetic target DNA input, using 10 nM blue dCas9-SB:gRNA_CT011, 1 nM blue dCas9-LB:gRNA_CT012, 20 nM green dCas9-SB:gRNA_NG, 2 nM green dCas9-LB:gRNA_NG and 250 pM of red calibrator in a single 20 μ L reaction. Individual replicate traces (n = 2) are shown.

Figure S20 | Green/Red and Blue/Red ratios of final one-pot duplex CT/NG RPA-LUNAS assay without bleed-through correction. Assays were performed with 10 – 10,000 cp of synthetic target DNA input, using 10 nM blue dCas9-SB:gRNA_CT011, 1 nM blue dCas9-LB:gRNA_CT012, 20 nM green dCas9-SB:gRNA_NG, 2 nM green dCas9-LB:gRNA_NG and 250 pM of red calibrator in a single 20 μ L reaction. Individual replicate traces ($n = 2$) are shown, with a rolling average filter (5-point centered) applied to the luminescence readings.

Sample nr	Measured concentration (copies/ μ L)	Dilution factor (sample * rxn)	Concentration in sample (copies/ μ L)	Coefficient of variation if n > 1
24	36.0	1 * 2.2	79.2	N/A
26	76.3	100 * 2.2	16791.5	N/A
27	16.9	20 * 2.2	744.6	4.2
33	26.6	20 * 2.2	1172.0	3.3
40	123.9	2 * 2.2	545.0	2.8
43	47.3	5 * 2.2	519.7	N/A
45	33.7	100 * 2.2	7413.5	0.1
54	198.3	10 * 2.2	4363.1	2.1
55	14.4	5 * 2.2	158.1	N/A
56	73.0	3 * 2.2	481.8	0.8
57	20.9	20 * 2.2	918.1	7.9

Figure S21 | Target load determination of NG-positive clinical samples using droplet-digital PCR (ddPCR). Top: overview of measured target loads and calculated clinical sample target load. Bottom: visualization of fluorescence intensities for all droplets per clinical samples. Blue circles indicate positive droplets and grey circles indicate negative droplets. Pink lines indicates fluorescence intensity threshold above which droplets are considered positive. Standard deviations are reported for samples with n = 2 technical replicates.

Sample nr	Measured concentration (copies/ μ L)	Dilution factor (sample * rxn)	Concentration in sample (copies/ μ L)	Coefficient of variation if n > 1
4	66.2	10 * 2.2	1455.2	1.7
5	41.7	50 * 2.2	4591.8	4.6
12	37.9	10 * 2.2	832.7	2.3
14	45.4	10 * 2.2	999.1	N/A
18	65.8	2 * 2.2	289.4	N/A
43	44.8	5 * 2.2	492.7	3.0
45	26.2	2 * 2.2	115.2	2.6
54	42.9	10 * 2.2	942.9	N/A
55	189.0	5 * 2.2	2078.7	N/A
56	24.9	3 * 2.2	164.3	1.1
57	50.3	20 * 2.2	2211.7	4.0

Figure S22 | Target load determination of CT-positive clinical samples using droplet-digital PCR (ddPCR). Top: overview of measured target loads and calculated clinical sample target load. Bottom: visualization of fluorescence intensities for all droplets per clinical samples. Blue circles indicate positive droplets and grey circles indicate negative droplets. Pink lines indicates fluorescence intensity threshold above which droplets are considered positive. Standard deviations are reported for samples with n = 2 technical replicates.

Figure S23 | Log-linear correlation between ddPCR target concentrations and qPCR CT values. ddPCR-determined target concentrations (omcB and TFPP gene for CT and NG, respectively) are plotted against the C_t values determined by the commercial Presto 100 CT/NG qPCR Kit . A linear regression model was fitted to the log-transformed data: $\log_{10}(y) = a + b \cdot x$, with y = target concentration and x = qPCR C_t value. Circles represent individual data points and red lines indicate model fit with 95% confidence bands. Exact fitting parameters are indicated in each graph.

Figure S24 | Plater reader traces of multiplex RPA-LUNAS on NG-positive, CT-positive and double-positive DNA isolates from clinical samples. Traces are grouped in panels per assay run. Left panels display blue/red ratios (458 nm / 653 nm, blue LUNAS, CT) and right panels display green/red ratios (533 nm / 653 nm, green LUNAS, NG). In the legend, the sample number is followed by the corresponding NG/CT presto qPCR Ct value in brackets.

Figure S25 | qPCR sample 12 *Neisseria Gonorrhoeae* targeting the TFPP gen. Sample 12 shows an increase in fluorescence (C_t value = 27.0), indicating the presence of NG DNA. Positive control DNA consists of DNA isolated from NG at 100 CFU/10 μ l.

Figure S26 | Camera traces of multiplex RPA-LUNAS on NG-positive, CT-positive and double-positive DNA isolates from clinical samples. Left panel displays blue/red ratios (458 nm / 653 nm, blue LUNAS, CT) and right panel displays green/red ratios (533 nm / 653 nm, green LUNAS, NG). In the legend, the sample number is followed by the corresponding NG/CT presto qPCR C_t value in brackets. Dashed lines represent set threshold.

Protein coding sequences and translations

SpdCas9-mNeonGreen-LargeBiT

Only the final 8 codons and residues of SpdCas9 are shown, the rest of its sequence being the same as previously described². Color codes: SpdCas9 highlighted in yellow; LargeBiTΔN4 in blue; mNeonGreenΔC10 in green, Strep-tag II in plum.

```
gatttgagtcagctaggaggtgacaccgggtgggggtagcggcggtcgggggtagtggt
D L S Q L G G D T G G G S G G S G G S G
ggaagcgggggttcaaagcttactagtatggtaagtaaagggtgaagaagacaatatggct
G S G G S K L T S M V S K G E E D N M A
tctctgcctgccacatgagcttcatatTTTTGGGagcataaacggagtggtgatttcgac
S L P A T H E L H I F G S I N G V D F D
atggtaggtcagggtacggggaaccctaacgatggatatgaggagttgaatcttaaagc
M V G Q G T G N P N D G Y E E L N L K S
acaaagggatctgcagttctgcacctggatcctgggtgccgcatataggttatggtttc
T K G D L Q F S P W I L V P H I G Y G F
catcagtatcttccatacccgatggcatgagccTTTTcaggccgcaatggtagatggc
H Q Y L P Y P D G M S P F Q A A M V D G
tcaggatatcaagtgcacgaccatgcagtttgaagatggggcgtctttgacggtaa
S G Y Q V H R T M Q F E D G A S L T V N
tacaggtacacctatgagggtagccatataaagggagaagcgcaggtgaagggaactgga
Y R Y T Y E G S H I K G E A Q V K G T G
ttcccagcggatggcccagtcacatgacaaacagcctcaccgctgctgattggtgccgatcc
F P A D G P V M T N S L T A A D W C R S
aagaaaacgtatccaaacgataaaaactatcatttctacttttaagtggctctatacaaca
K K T Y P N D K T I I S T F K W S Y T T
ggaaacgggaaacgctatcgttcaacggcccgcacgacctacacgtttgcaaagccaatg
G N G K R Y R S T A R T T Y T F A K P M
gctgcaattatctgaaaaaccagccgatgtatgtgttccgtaaaaccgaactgaaacat
A A N Y L K N Q P M Y V F R K T E L K H
tctaaaacggagctcaatttcaaggaatggcagaaggcatttaccggttttgaagatttc
S K T E L N F K E W Q K A F T G F E D F
gttggggactgggaacagacagccgcctacaacctggaccaagtccttgaacagggaggt
V G D W E Q T A A Y N L D Q V L E Q G G
gtgtccagtttgctgcagaatctcgccgtgtccgtaactccgatccaaaggattgtccgg
V S S L L Q N L A V S V T P I Q R I V R
agcggtgaaaatgcctgaagatcgacatccatgtcatcatcccgtatgaaggctctgagc
S G E N A L K I D I H V I I P Y E G L S
gccgaccaaattggcccagatcgaagaggtgtttaagggtggtgtaccctgtggatgatcat
A D Q M A Q I E E V F K V V Y P V D D H
cactttaagggtgatcctgccctatggcacactggtaatcgacggggttacgccgaacatg
H F K V I L P Y G T L V I D G V T P N M
ctgaactatttccgacggccgtatgaaggcatcgccgtgttcgacggcaaaaagatcact
L N Y F G R P Y E G I A V F D G K K I T
gtaacagggaccctgtggaacggcaacaaaattatcgacgagcgcctgatcacccccgac
V T G T L W N G N K I I D E R L I T P D
ggctccatgctgttccgagtaaccatcaacagcgggtggaagctggagccatccgcagttt
G S M L F R V T I N S G G S W S H P Q F
gaaaaataa
E K -
```

SpdCas9-LargeBiT-mNeonGreen

Only the final 8 codons and residues of SpdCas9 are shown, the rest of its sequence being the same as previously described². Color codes: SpdCas9 highlighted in **yellow**; LargeBiT in **blue**; mNeonGreen Δ C10 in **green**, Strep-tag II in **plum**.

```
gatttgagtcagctaggaggtgacaccgggtgggggtagcggcggtcggggggtagtggt
D L S Q L G G D T G G G S G G S G G S G
ggaagcgggggttcaaagcttactagtgtcttcacactcgaagatttcggtggggactgg
G S G G S K L T S V F T L E D F V G D W
gaacagacagccgcctacaacctggaccaagtccttgaacagggaggtgtgtccagtttg
E Q T A A Y N L D Q V L E Q G G V S S L
ctgcagaatctcgcctgtccgtaactccgatccaaaggattgtccggagcggtgaaaat
L Q N L A V S V T P I Q R I V R S G E N
gccctgaagatcgacatccatgtcatcatcccgtatgaaggctctgagcgcggaccaaatg
A L K I D I H V I I P Y E G L S A D Q M
gccagatcgaagaggtgtttaaggtggtgtaccctgtggatgatcatcactttaaggtg
A Q I E E V F K V V Y P V D D H H F K V
atcctgccctatggcacactggtaatcgacgggggttacgccgaacatgctgaactatttc
I L P Y G T L V I D G V T P N M L N Y F
ggacggccgtatgaaggcatcgccgtgttcgacggcaaaaagatcactgtaacagggacc
G R P Y E G I A V F D G K K I T V T G T
ctgtggaacggcaacaaaattatcgacgagcgcctgatccccccgacggctccatgctg
L W N G N K I I D E R L I T P D G S M L
ttccgagtaaccatcaacagcatggtaagtaaaggtgaagaagacaatatggcttctctg
F R V T I N S M V S K G E E D N M A S L
cctgccacacatgagcttcataatTTTTGGGAGCATAAACGGAGTGGATTTGACATGGTA
P A T H E L H I F G S I N G V D F D M V
ggtcagggtagcggggaaccctaacgatggatatgaggagttgaatcttaaaagcacaaag
G Q G T G N P N D G Y E E L N L K S T K
ggtgatctgcagttctcgcctggatcctggtgccgcataataggttatggtttccatcag
G D L Q F S P W I L V P H I G Y G F H Q
tatcttccataaccggatggcatgagcccttttcaggccgcaatggtagatggctcagga
Y L P Y P D G M S P F Q A A M V D G S G
tatcaagtgcacggaccatgcagtttgaagatggggcgtctttgacggtaaattacagg
Y Q V H R T M Q F E D G A S L T V N Y R
tacacctatgagggtagccatataaagggagaagcgcaggtgaaggggaactggattcca
Y T Y E G S H I K G E A Q V K G T G F P
gcgatggcccagtcatgacaaacagcctcaccgctgctgattgggtgccgatccaagaaa
A D G P V M T N S L T A A D W C R S K K
acgatccaaacgataaaaactatcatttctacttttaagtggctctatacaacaggaaac
T Y P N D K T I I S T F K W S Y T T G N
gggaaacgctatcgttcaacggcccgcacgacctacagtttgcaaagccaatggctgcg
G K R Y R S T A R T T Y T F A K P M A A
aattatctgaaaaaccagccgatgtatgtgttccgtaaaaccgaactgaaacattctaaa
N Y L K N Q P M Y V F R K T E L K H S K
acggagctcaatttcaaggaatggcagaaggcatttaccgggtggaagctggagccatccg
T E L N F K E W Q K A F T G G S W S H P
cagtttgaaaaataa
Q F E K -
```

SpdCas9-mNeonGreen-SmallBiT

Only the final 8 codons and residues of SpdCas9 are shown, the rest of its sequence being the same as previously described². Color codes: SpdCas9 highlighted in yellow; SmallBiT in cyan; mNeonGreen Δ C10 in green, Strep-tag II in plum.

```
gatttgagtcagctaggaggtgacaccgggtgggggtagcggcgggctcggggggtagtgg  
D L S Q L G G D T G G G S G G S G G S G  
ggaagcgggggttcaaagcttactagtgggtcatatggtaagtaaagggtgaagaagacaat  
G S G G S K L T S G H M V S K G E E D N  
atggcttctctgcctgccacacatgagcttcatatTTTTGGGagcataaacggagtgat  
M A S L P A T H E L H I F G S I N G V D  
ttcgacatggtaggtcagggtagcggggaaccctaacgatggatatgaggagttgaatctt  
F D M V G Q G T G N P N D G Y E E L N L  
aaaagcaciaaagggtgatctgcagttctgcacctggatcctggtgccgcatataggttat  
K S T K G D L Q F S P W I L V P H I G Y  
ggtttccatcagtatcttccataaccggatggcatgagccctttcaggccgcaatggta  
G F H Q Y L P Y P D G M S P F Q A A M V  
gatggctcaggatatcaagtgcacatcgaccatgcagtttgaagatggggcgtctttgacg  
D G S G Y Q V H R T M Q F E D G A S L T  
gtaaattacaggtacacctatgagggtagccatataaagggagaagcgcaggtgaagggga  
V N Y R Y T Y E G S H I K G E A Q V K G  
actggattcccagcggatggcccagtcacgacaacagcctcaccgctgctgattgggtgc  
T G F P A D G P V M T N S L T A A D W C  
cgatccaagaaaacgtatccaaacgataaaaactatcatttctacttttaagtggtcctat  
R S K K T Y P N D K T I I S T F K W S Y  
acaacaggaacgggaaacgctatcgttcaacggcccgcacgacctacacgtttgcaaag  
T T G N G K R Y R S T A R T T Y T F A K  
ccaatggctgcaattatctgaaaaaccagccgatgtatgtgttccgtaaaaccgaactg  
P M A A N Y L K N Q P M Y V F R K T E L  
aacatttctaaaacggagctcaatttcaaggaatggcagaaggcatttaccggtagcgtc  
K H S K T E L N F K E W Q K A F T G S V  
accggctatcggctctttgagaagaatctggaggttctggcggatcttgggtcccatccg  
T G Y R L F E K E S G G S G G S W S H P  
cagtttgaaaaataa  
Q F E K -
```

SpdCas9-SmallBiT-mNeonGreen

Only the final 8 codons and residues of SpdCas9 are shown, the rest of its sequence being the same as previously described². Color codes: SpdCas9 highlighted in yellow; SmallBiT in cyan; mNeonGreen Δ C10 in green, Strep-tag II in plum.

```
gatttgagtcagctaggaggtgacaccgggtgggggtagcggcggtcgggggtagtggt
D L S Q L G G D T G G G S G G S G G S G
ggaagcgggggttcaaagcttactagtgttaccggctatcgtctgtttgaaaaagagagc
G S G G S K L T S V T G Y R L F E K E S
atggtaagtaaaggtgaagaagacaatatggcttctctgcctgccacacatgagcttcat
M V S K G E E D N M A S L P A T H E L H
atTTTTgggagcataaacggagtggtttcgacatggtaggtcagggtagcggggaaccct
I F G S I N G V D F D M V G Q G T G N P
aacgatggatatgaggagttgaatcttaaaagcacaagggtgatctgcagttctcgccc
N D G Y E E L N L K S T K G D L Q F S P
tggatcctggtgcccatatagggttatggtttccatcagtatcttccataccggatggc
W I L V P H I G Y G F H Q Y L P Y P D G
atgagcccttttcaggccgcaatggtagatggctcaggatcaagtgcacatcgaccatg
M S P F Q A A M V D G S G Y Q V H R T M
cagtttgaagatggggcgcttttgacggtaaattacaggtacacctatgagggttagccat
Q F E D G A S L T V N Y R Y T Y E G S H
ataaagggagaagcgcaggtgaaggaactggattcccagcggatggcccagtcatgaca
I K G E A Q V K G T G F P A D G P V M T
aacagcctcaccgctgctgattggtgccgatccaagaaaacgtatccaacgataaaact
N S L T A A D W C R S K K T Y P N D K T
atcatttctacttttaagtggtcctatacaacaggaaacgggaaacgctatcgttcaacg
I I S T F K W S Y T T G N G K R Y R S T
gcccgcacgacctacacgtttgcaaagccaatggctgogaattatctgaaaaaccagccg
A R T T Y T F A K P M A A N Y L K N Q P
atgtatgtgttccgtaaaaccgaactgaaacattctaaaacggagctcaatttcaaggaa
M Y V F R K T E L K H S K T E L N F K E
tggcagaaggcatttaccggatccgggtggaagctggagccatccgcagtttgaaaaataa
W Q K A F T G S G G S W S H P Q F E K -
```

SpdCas9-SmallBiT with K-4C and S+2C mutation positions indicated

Only the final 8 codons and residues of SpdCas9 are shown, the rest of its sequence being the same as previously described². Color codes: SpdCas9 highlighted in yellow; SmallBiT in cyan; Strep-tag II in plum; mutations K-4C in red font; S+2C in orange.

```
gatttgagtcagctaggaggtgacaccgggtgggggtagcggcggtcgggggtagtggt
D L S Q L G G D T G G G S G G S G G S G
ggaagcgggggttcaaagccttactagtgttaccggctatcgtctgtttgaaaaagagagc
G S G G S K L T S V T G Y R L F E K E S
ggatccgggtggaagctggagccatccgcagtttgaaaaataa
G S G G S W S H P Q F E K -
```

SpdCas9-LargeBiT with T41C and G66C mutation positions indicated

Only the final 8 codons and residues of SpdCas9 are shown, the rest of its sequence being the same as previously described². Color codes: SpdCas9 highlighted in yellow; LargeBiT in blue; Strep-tag II in plum; mutation positions T41C in red font; G66C in orange.

```
gatttgagtcagctaggaggtgacaccgggtgggggtagcggcggtcgggggtagtggt
D L S Q L G G D T G G G S G G S G G S G
ggaagcgggggttcaaagcttactagtgtcttcacactcgaagatttcggtggggactgg
G S G G S K L T S V F T L E D F V G D W
gaacagacagccgcctacaacctggaccaagtccttgaacagggaggtgtgtccagtttg
E Q T A A Y N L D Q V L E Q G G V S S L
ctgcagaatctcgccgtgtccgtaacctccgatccaaaggattgtccggagcggtgaaaat
L Q N L A V S V T P I Q R I V R S G E N
gccctgaagatcgacatccatgtcatcatcccgtatgaaggctctgagcgcggaccaaatg
A L K I D I H V I I P Y E G L S A D Q M
gccagatcgaagaggtgtttaaggtggtgtaccctgtggatgatcatcactttaaggtg
A Q I E E V F K V V Y P V D D H H F K V
atcctgccctatggcacactggtaatcgacgggggttacgccgaacatgctgaactatctc
I L P Y G T L V I D G V T P N M L N Y F
ggacggccgtatgaaggcatcgccgtgttcgacggcaaaaagatcactgtaacagggacc
G R P Y E G I A V F D G K K I T V T G T
ctgtggaacggcaacaaaattatcgacgagcgcctgatcccccgacggctccatgctg
L W N G N K I I D E R L I T P D G S M L
ttccgagtaaccatcaacagcgggtggaagctggagccatccgcagtttgaaaaataa
F R V T I N S G G S W S H P Q F E K -
```

NanoLuc_C166S with T41C, G66C, S68C, G113C, G136C, D148C, G159C mutation positions indicated

Color codes: NanoLuc in cyan; Strep-tag II in plum; mutation positions T41C in red font; G66C in orange, S68C in green, G113C in purple, G136C in gold, D148C in dark red, G159C in pink.

```
atgtgggtctcatcctcaatttgaaaaaatggatatttactcttgaagattttgtcggtgat
M W S H P Q F E K M V F T L E D F V G D
tggcgccagaccgcccgtataacctggaccaagtgttgaacagggcggggtagcagc
W R Q T A G Y N L D Q V L E Q G G V S S
ctgtttcaaacctgggggtgagtgtaacgccaattcagcgcacatcgttctgtcgggagag
L F Q N L G V S V T P I Q R I V L S G E
aatggctctgaaaatcgatatccacgtcattatcccgtacgaaaggctcttctgggtgatcag
N G L K I D I H V I I P Y E G L S G D Q
atggggcagatagaaaaaatattcaaagtgggtgtaccagtagacgatcatcacttcaag
M G Q I E K I F K V V Y P V D D H H F K
gttatactgcactatggcaccctcggtatcgatggcggttactccgaatatgatcgattac
V I L H Y G T L V I D G V T P N M I D Y
tttggcgctccttatgaaggtattgcccgtgttcgacggtaaaaaaattacggttaccggg
F G R P Y E G I A V F D G K K I T V T G
acgctctggaatggtaataaaatcattgatgagcgttgataaacccagatggcagcctt
T L W N G N K I I D E R L I N P D G S L
ctgttcagagttacgataaacgggggttacggggtggcgactgagcgaagaatattagct
L F R V T I N G V T G W R L S E R I L A
gccccgcactcgagctgccagaaaccgggtggccaccaccaccaccactga
A A A L E L P E T G G H H H H H H -
```

NanoBiT calibrator luciferase with T41C mutation position indicated

Color codes: NanoBiT in cyan; mutation position T41C in red font.

```
atgggcagcagccatcatcatcatcatcacagcagcggcctggtgcccgcggcagccat
M G S S H H H H H H S S G L V P R G S H
atggaagatttcggtggggactgggaacagacagccgcctacaacctggaccaagtcctt
M E D F V G D W E Q T A A Y N L D Q V L
gaacagggagggtgtgtccagtttgctgcagaatctcgccgtgtccgtaactccgatccaa
E Q G G V S S L L Q N L A V S V T P I Q
aggattgtccggagcgggtgaaaatgccctgaagatcgacatccatgtcatcatcccgtat
R I V R S G E N A L K I D I H V I I P Y
gaaggtctgagcgcggaccaaattggcccagatcgaagaggtgtttaagggtggtgtaccct
E G L S A D Q M A Q I E E V F K V V Y P
gtggatgatcatcactttaagggtgatcctgcccctatggcacactggtaatcgacggggtt
V D D H H F K V I L P Y G T L V I D G V
acgccgaacatgctgaactatctcgacggccgtatgaaggcatcgccgtgttcgacggc
T P N M L N Y F G R P Y E G I A V F D G
aaaaagatcactgtaacagggaccctgtggaacggcaacaaaattatcgacgagcgcctg
K K I T V T G T L W N G N K I I D E R L
atcacccccgacggctccatgctgttccgagtaaccatcaacggatctggtggctcaggt
I T P D G S M L F R V T I N G S G G S G
ggtagtggaggatcaggaggtagtggcggatcaggtaccgttaccggctatcgctctgttt
G S G G S G G S G G S G T V T G Y R L F
gaaaaagagagcgggtgggttcacatcatcaccatcaccactaa
E K E S G G S H H H H H H -
```

Sequences of target DNA fragments used for initial assay development.

Synthetic DNA fragment with T7 phage protospacers (50 bp interspace)

GTCAAGCTGCTGATGATGCTGAGCACCCGGGATAACTGGTAAGCCTTGGGTTTCAGGCTGGCATCGATGC
ATGCTCATTCGATGGCATCGACGCATCCGGTCTTGAGCTACGCTGCTTGGCTCACTTCATGGCTCGAC
CGGTTAACGGCGAGTACGCTCACGAGACCACGGCCTGAGCTATAACTGCTCCCTTCCGCTGGCGTTTG
ACGGGTCTTGCTCTGGCATCCAGCACTTCTGTGCTCGCTTCCGCTGCATCCTGCACTTCTCCGCGATG
CTCCGAGATGAGGTAGGTGGTCGCGCGGTTAACTTGCTTACTAGTGAAACGCTCACCGAGGGATTAG
CGGTATGATTGCATCACCACTTCATCCCTATAGAGTCAAGTCCTAAGGTATACCCATAAAGAGCTA
GAGATAGATCACCACTTCATTATACCCGATAAAGAGCCTCTAATGGTCTATCCTAAGGTCTATACAGA
TCATCCTGTGCTGTCACCTGAG

SARS-CoV-2 – ORF1a cDNA fragment

TAATACGACTCACTATAGGGGAAAGGTAAGATGGAGAGCCTTGTCCCTGGTTTCAACGAGAAAACACA
CGTCCAACCTCAGTTTGCCTGTTTTACAGGTTTCGCGACGTGCTCGTACGTGGCTTTGGAGACTCCGTGG
AGGAGGTCTTATCAGAGGCACGTCAACATCTTAAAGATGGCACTTGTGGCTTAGTAGAAGTTGAAAAA
GGCGTTTTGCCTCAACTTGAACAGCCCTATGTGTTTCATCAAACGTTTCGGATGCTCGAACTGCACCTCA
TGGTCATGTTATGGTTGAGCTGGTAGCAGAACTCGAAGGCATTCAGTACGGTCGTAGTGGTGAGACAC
TTGGTGTCCCTTGTCCCTCATGTGGGCGAAATACCAGTGGCTTACCGCAAGGTTCTTCTTCGTAAGAAC
GGTAATAAAGGAGCTGGTGGCCATAGTTACGGCGCCGATCTAAAGTCATTTGACTTAGGCGACGAGCT
TGGCACTGATCCTTATGAAGATTTTCAAGAAAACCTGGAACACTAAACATAGCGCTTCGCTAGGCCGC
TGAGCAATAACTAGCATAACCCCTTGGGGCCTCTAAACGGGTCTTGAGGGGTTTTTTGCTGAAAACCT
CGCTCGCTGAGGTGTCAATCGTCGGAGCCGCTGAGCAATAACTAGCATAACCCCTTGGGGCCTCTAAA
CGGGTCTTGAGGGGTTTTTTGCATGGTCATAGCTGTTTTCTG

Human – RPP30 cDNA fragment

TAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGACCCAAGCTGGCTAGCGTTTAACTTAAGCTTGGTACCGAGCTCGG
ATCCGCCACCATGGCGGTGTTTTGCAGATTTGGACCTGCGAGCGGGTCTGACCTGAAGGCTCTGCGCG
GACTTGTGGAGACAGCCGCTCACCTTGGCTATTCAGTTGTTGCTATCAATCATATCGTTGACTTTAAG
GAAAAGAAACAGGAAATTGAAAAACCAGTAGCTGTTTCTGAACTCTTCACAACTTTGCCAATTGTACA
GGGAAAATCAAGACCAATTAATAATTTTAACTAGATTAACAATTAATTGTCTCGGATCCATCTCACTGCA
ATGTTTTGAGAGCAACTTCTTCAAGGGCCCGGCTCTATGATGTTGTTGCAGTTTTTCCAAAGACAGAA
AAGCTTTTTTCATATTGCTTGCACACATTTAGATGTGGATTTAGTCTGCATAACTGTAACAGAGAACT
ACCATTTTACTTCAAAGACCTCCTATTAATGTGGCGATTGACCGAGGCCTGGCTTTTTGAACTTGTCT
ATAGCCCTGCTATCAAAGACTCCACAATGAGAAGGTATAACAATTTCCAGTGCCCTCAATTTGATGCAA
ATCTGCAAAGGAAAGAATGTAATTATATCTAGTGTGTCAGAAAGGCCTTTAGAAATAAGAGGGCCATA
TGACGTGGCAAATCTAGGCTTGTGTTTTGGGCTCTCTGAAAGTGACGCCAAGGCTGCGGTGTCCACCA
ACTGCCGAGCAGCGCTTCTCCATGGAGAACTAGAAAAACTGCTTTTTGGAATTATCTCTACAGTGAAG
AAACCTCGGCCATCAGAAGGAGATGAAGATTGTCTTCCAGCTTCCAAGAAAGCCAAGTGTGAGGGCGA
TTACAAGGATGACGACGATAAGTGA

Chlamydia trachomatis - uvrC gene

GCAGCCTTGTATCGCACTCTCACCCCTGATCCGTCAAACCTATGGCAAACAGCATGTTGAGAAATTTCA
AGCATATGATATCGATGTACTAGGCCTTTATAGGAAAGGTTCTCTCGCTATTGTCTCTGTACTATCCG
TCTATTCTGGGAAACTACTTGGCGCTCGTTATTTTTATCTTCCCAGAAAATGCTCAGGAAGATTCTGCC
TTATTTTTCTTCTTTCATTTTTGCAATATTATGCAGAAAATCCTCGTATCCCCAAGGAAATATTTGTTCC
TGTATCTTTAGACAGTCCAGAGCTCCCCTATCTACTGAACACTGCTGAACCGCCAAAAATCCGCTGCC
CGAAAACAGAATACGGAAAAGAGCTTCTTGCTCTTGCTCATAAAAATGCTGCTGAACAAGCGAAACCT

TTCAATTCTATCACTCCTCCTTATGAAGAGCTGCAACATTTCTTTAATTTAAGCCAGTATCCATATCG
CATTGAGTGCTATGACAATGCACACTTACAAGGTGAGCATAATGTCGGTGTGTGCATTGTTTTCGAAA
ATGGTCTCTTCTCTCCCAAACAATATCGCACCTTCTCTATTACTTCTCATGGCGATGACTTGGCTGCT
TTTGAAGAGGTCTTAACACGACGTTTCCGATCCCTTACTACAGAACTCCCAAACCTTAATAGTAATCGA
TGGTGGACGTAATCAATTTAAACGAGCGCAACGCATTTTAGAGGAGCTGAATTTAACAGGGATTACCG
TAGTAACCATCGCCAAGGAATCTGGCAATCACAGCAAAGCTTGCGCCAAGAAAAGCTATTTTGTGAA
A

Neisseria Gonnorrhoeae - dcmH gene

CAGAATATCGGTTATTCGGTGGAAATGTAAGATACTGAGTGCAGCCGATTTTCGGTGTTCCTCAGATACG
TAGCCGAGTGATATTTATCGGGAGGAGGGATAAAGGCCAAAATTTCTTTCCCGAACCTTTGCAGATTT
CCCATCAGACTGTTGGATCAGCAATAGGACATTTTCCAAAACCTGGCTGCTGGCGAAAGCAATCCACAC
GTTGCAAATCATGAAGCTATGAATCATTTCGGCACAAATGTTAGAAAAAATGGCATTG

Supplementary Tables

Table S1 | gRNA sequences. Only the spacer sequence is shown.

T7 phage		Target: T7 synthetic target
T7_A	T7 gRNA set	GCGUUUGACGGGUCUUGCUC
T7_B	T7 gRNA set	UACCUCAUCUCGGAGCAUCG

SARS-CoV-2		Target: ORF1a
SC2ORF1a_A	SARS-CoV-2 gRNA set	GGUCGUAGUGGUGAGACACU
SC2ORF1a_B	SARS-CoV-2 gRNA set	AGAACCUUGCGGUAAGCCAC

Human		Target: RPP30 mRNA / cDNA
HsRPP30_A	HsRPP30 gRNA set	AAUUUGAUGCAAUCUGCAA
HsRPP30_B	HsRPP30 gRNA set	UAUGGCCUCUCUUAUUUCUAA

Chlamydia Trachomatis		Target: uvrC gene
CT011	CT gRNA set 1	AUUGCCAGAUUCCUUGGCCGA
CT012	CT gRNA set 1	ACGAGCGCAACGCAUUUUAG
CT013	CT gRNA set 2	GGAGUUCUGUAGUAAGGGAU
CT014	CT gRNA set 2	UACUUCUCAUGGCCGAUGACU
CT001	CT gRNA A	GCAUAUGAUUAUCGAUGUACU
CT002	CT gRNA A	UCGAUGUACUAGGCCUUUUAU
CT003	CT gRNA A	GUACUAGGCCUUUUAUAGGAA
CT007	CT gRNA B	AAGUAGUUUCCCAGAAUAGA

Neisseria Gonnorrhoea		Target: dcmH gene
NG003	NG gRNA A	GAGUGAUUUUAUCGGGAGG
NG004	NG gRNA A	AGUGAUUUUAUCGGGAGGA
NG008	NG gRNA B	GUCUGAUGGGAAAUCUGCAA
NG009	NG gRNA B	UGCUGAUCCAACAGUCUGAU

Final duplex CT + NG assay		
NG004	NG gRNA A	AGUGAUUUUAUCGGGAGGA
NG008	NG gRNA B	GUCUGAUGGGAAAUCUGCAA
CT011	CT gRNA set 1	AUUGCCAGAUUCCUUGGCCGA
CT012	CT gRNA set 1	ACGAGCGCAACGCAUUUUAG

Table S2 | RPA Primers

SARS-CoV-2		Target: ORF1a
SC2ORF1a.F	SARS-CoV-2 RPA forward primer	GCTGGTAGCAGAACTCGAAGGCATTTCAGTAC
SC2ORF1a.R	SARS-CoV-2 RPA reverse primer	ACCAGCTCCTTTATTACCGTTCTTACGAAGA

Human		Target: RPP30 mRNA / cDNA
HsRPP30.F	HsRPP30 RPA forward primer	AATGAGAAGGTATACAATTTCCAGTGCCCTC
HsRPP30.R	HsRPP30 RPA reverse primer	GAGCCCAAACAGCAAGCCTAGATTGTCACG

Chlamydia Trachomatis		Target: uvrC gene
JC013	CT RPA forward primer 1	GGGGATACGAGGATTTTCTGCATAATATTGC
JC014	CT RPA forward primer 2	CAAATATTTCTTGGGGATACGAGGATTTTCTGC
JC015	CT RPA forward primer 3	GGCAGAATCTTCTGAGCATTCTTGGGAA
JC016	CT RPA reverse primer 1	GGCAAAACAGCATGTTGAGAAATTTCAAGC
JC017	CT RPA reverse primer 2	GCATGTTGAGAAATTTCAAGCATATGATATCG
JC018	CT RPA reverse primer 3	CCGTCAAACATATGGCAAAACAGCATGTTGAG
JC030	CT RPA forward primer 2.1	CAAATAGCTTTTCTTGGCGCAAGCTTTTGCTG
JC031	CT RPA forward primer 2.2	GGGGAAAGTTTACAAAATAGCTTTTCTTGG
JC032	CT RPA forward primer 2.3	GGATTCTTGGGGGAAAGTTTACAAAATAGC
JC033	CT RPA reverse primer 2.1	CTCCCAAACAATATCGCACCTTCTCTATTAC
JC034	CT RPA reverse primer 2.2	AATGGTCTCTTCTCTCCCAAACAATATCGC
JC035	CT RPA reverse primer 2.3	GTGCATTGTTTTCGAAAATGGTCTTCTCTCCC
JC036	CT RPA reverse primer 3.1	GGTGGACGTAATCAATTTAAACGAGCGCAACGC
JC037	CT RPA reverse primer 3.2	CGATGGTGGACGTAATCAATTTAAACGAGCG
JC038	CT RPA reverse primer 3.3	GTAATCGATGGTGGACGTAATCAATTTAAACG
JC039	CT RPA reverse primer 3.4	CTCCCAAACCTTAATAGTAATCGATGGTGGACG

Neisseria Gonorrhoea		Target: dcmH gene
JC019	NG RPA forward primer 1	GTAAGATACTGAGTGCAGCCGATTTCCGGTG
JC020	NG RPA forward primer 2	CGGTGGAATGTAAGATACTGAGTGCAGCCG
JC021	NG RPA forward primer 3	CAGAATATCGGTTATTCGGTGGAATGTAAG
JC022	NG RPA forward primer 4	GTGCAGCCGATTTCCGGTGTCCCTCAGATACG
JC023	NG RPA reverse primer 1	CAAATGCCATTTTTCTAACATTTGTGCCGAATG
JC024	NG RPA reverse primer 2	CAAATGCCATTTTTCTAACATTTGTGCCG
JC025	NG RPA reverse primer 3	CATTTGTGCCGAATGATTCATAGCTTCATG

Final duplex CT + NG assay		
JC030	CT RPA forward primer 2.1	CAAATAGCTTTTCTTGGCGCAAGCTTTTGCTG
JC038	CT RPA reverse primer 3.3	GTAATCGATGGTGGACGTAATCAATTTAAACG
JC021	NG RPA forward primer 3	CAGAATATCGGTTATTCGGTGGAATGTAAG
JC023	NG RPA reverse primer 1	CAAATGCCATTTTTCTAACATTTGTGCCGAATG

Table S3 | Overview clinical samples with qPCR, ddPCR and LUNAS data

CT positives			PRESTO qPCR Ct values		ddPCR [target] (copies/µL)		LUNAS threshold times - platerader (minutes)			LUNAS threshold times - camera (minutes)					
No	Gender	Specimen	Origin	CT	NG	CT	NG	CT-1	CT-2	NG-1	NG-2	CT-1	CT-2	NG-1	NG-2
004	M	HUI	REM	25.57	not detected	1455.2	not tested	9.91	10.67	not detected	not detected	10	10	not detected	not detected
005	M	HUI	REM	23.25	not detected	4591.8	not tested	8.41	9.91	not detected	not detected	10	10	not detected	not detected
009	M	BOL	KEE	28.97	not detected	not tested	not tested	14.42	17.42	not detected	not detected	not tested	not tested	not tested	not tested
012	F	BOL	KEE	25.2	not detected	832.7	not tested	10.67	12.17	18.92	20.42	10	10	not tested	40
014	F	GEN	VAG	25.14	not detected	989.1	not tested	9.91	14.42	not detected	not detected	not tested	not tested	not tested	not tested
018	F	HUI	REM	27.28	not detected	289.4	not tested	9.91	12.17	not detected	not detected	not tested	not tested	not tested	not tested
NG positives															
No	Gender	Specimen	Origin	CT	NG	CT	NG	CT-1	CT-2	NG-1	NG-2	CT-1	CT-2	NG-1	NG-2
024	M	URI	-	not detected	27.20	not tested	79.2	not detected	not detected	23.42	29.42	not detected	not detected	52	36
026	M	URI	-	not detected	18.67	not tested	16791.5	not detected	not detected	14.41	15.92	not detected	not detected	22	22
027	M	URI	-	not detected	23.44	not tested	744.6	not detected	not detected	18.17	20.42	not detected	not detected	34	38
032	F	BOL	KEE	not detected	27.73	not tested	not tested	not detected	not detected	18.17	19.67	not tested	not tested	not tested	not tested
033	F	BOL	KEE	not detected	22.97	not tested	1172	not detected	not detected	14.41	14.41	not tested	not tested	not tested	not tested
040	F	HUI	REM	not detected	26.27	not tested	545	not detected	not detected	14.41	14.41	not tested	not tested	not tested	not tested
CT/NG double-positives															
No	Gender	Specimen	Origin	CT	NG	CT	NG	CT-1	CT-2	NG-1	NG-2	CT-1	CT-2	NG-1	NG-2
043	M	HUI	REM	26.69	24.84	492.7	519.7	9.92	12.91	18.17	19.67	18	20	40	40
045	M	HUI	REM	27.76	20.74	115.2	7415.5	13.67	24.17	12.17	12.91	30	20	24	18
054	F	HUI	REM	25.45	21.58	942.9	4363.1	9.91	11.42	14.41	15.97	24	22	24	22
055	F	GEN	VAG	24.01	25.86	2078.7	158.1	7.67	8.42	21.17	not detected	not tested	not tested	not tested	not tested
056	F	GEN	VAG	27.52	24.3	164.3	481.8	15.91	24.17	19.67	21.92	not tested	not tested	not tested	not tested
057	F	GEN	VAG	24.31	23.12	2211.7	918.1	7.68	11.42	16.67	19.67	not tested	not tested	not tested	not tested

M = male HUI = skin swab REM = rectal
 F = female BOL = upper respiratory swab KEE = throat
 GEN = genital swab VAG = vaginal
 URI = urine

Table S4 | ddPCR primers and probe sequences for Neisseria Gonorrhoea TFPP gene

Neisseria Gonorrhoea		Target: TFPP gene
fwd	NG ddPCR forward primer	ACACCCAATACCTGCCCGAC
rev	NG ddPCR reverse primer	CGGCAACCGCACCTAAAAC
probe	Fluorescent readout probe sequence	56-FAM/ACGGCGGCT/ZEN/TCGTGCCTTTGC/3IABkFQ

References

- (1) Geoghegan, K. F.; Dixon, H. B. F.; Rosner, P. J.; Hoth, L. R.; Lanzetti, A. J.; Borzilleri, K. A.; Marr, E. S.; Pezzullo, L. H.; Martin, L. B.; LeMotte, P. K.; McColl, A. S.; Kamath, A. V.; Stroh, J. G. Spontaneous α -N-6-Phosphogluconoylation of a “His Tag” in Escherichia Coli: The Cause of Extra Mass of 258 or 178 Da in Fusion Proteins. *Anal. Biochem.* **1999**, *267* (1), 169–184. <https://doi.org/10.1006/abio.1998.2990>.
- (2) van der Veer, H. J.; van Aalen, E. A.; Michielsen, C. M. S.; Hanckmann, E. T. L.; Deckers, J.; van Borren, M. M. G. J.; Flipse, J.; Loonen, A. J. M.; Schoeber, J. P. H.; Merkx, M. Glow-in-the-Dark Infectious Disease Diagnostics Using CRISPR-Cas9-Based Split Luciferase Complementation. *ACS Cent. Sci.* **2023**, *9* (4), 657–667. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscentsci.2c01467>.